

EVENT MANAGEMENT FOR AD HOC NETWORKS USING THE ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Different events that one can call mishappening can occur in the network, like any blast, network failure, and optimized use of batteries, are discussed. Identifying the faulty node or the node that becomes the victim of the event becomes highly complicated because the ad hoc network's nodes are not stationary. In this work, the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm is used to find the routes. Mitigation and identification are made using a neural network. The route discovery process involves event management using the ABC algorithm. A method to generate an ad hoc network for discovering route mechanisms involving identification and nodes' movement within the coverage area is introduced. This paper represents an enhanced approach to the route discovery mechanism using an artificial bee colony algorithm and the Levenberg neural network classification model identification of the faulty node.

Keywords: Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET), Event Management, Intrusion, Artificial Bee Colony, Levenberg Neural Network

INTRODUCTION

Ad hoc Networks (AHN's) are most likely to operate in the internet's outermost region while a cable backbone connects both the fixed local area networks and the mobile networks. Ad hoc networks often communicate by radio connection or satellite link, whereas the base stations of fixed infrastructure networks are directly connected to the core. As a result, we can conclude that ad hoc networks still need to be developed. Data is transferred from a node called a source node to a node called a destination node [2] in the wireless ad hoc mode. Through a number of nodes, data is transported from the source node to the destination node. To provide a path for the data to travel from source to destination, these intermediary nodes are used [3]. The type of topologies utilized in the network causes the distance between sources and destinations to change, therefore, to ensure that the network operates effectively in locations with limited power availability; batteries must be used as efficiently as possible [4]. More battery power is needed if the destination node is located far from the source node. As a result, we may conclude that battery usage is influenced by the distance between the source and the destination nodes. The battery [5] is used to carry out various tasks such as routing, trafficking, load balancing, and event management.

Setting up a route for data to travel on from source to destination is referred to as routing. Despite the fact that there are more than 20 routing algorithms, the ad hoc network experiences coverage and cost management issues [6]. The application of a trust model, which would spare the system any additional costs associated with finding a suitable node for data transfer, is the first challenge of this study work. No algorithm other than a swarm intelligence-based algorithm may be considered for such a purpose [7]. Here, the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) Algorithm would be used to achieve the goal. A set S of transceivers, where S is a number ranging from $0, 1, \dots, |S| - 1$, and their locations or separations from one another, serve as the representation of an ad hoc network. Each node's transmission power is represented by the symbol R_v , where $v \in S$. For each transmission pair (v, S) , with $v \in S$, their non-negative arc weight $e(v, S)$ allows for the reception of a signal from the transceiver v at node S if and only if the transmission power

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of v is at least equal to $e(v, S)$, or if $R_v \geq e(v, S)$. There are several reasons why a system could fail [8]. It may have happened because of a data overload, increased power use, potential risks to the load, or other potential occurrences.

A severe issue is when an unwanted occurrence happens in the MANET [9]. In this scenario, a malicious node makes use of the routing protocol to access the data by directing the node to the target node whose packets it wishes to intercept via the quickest route. The two sorts of attacks that can occur in an ad hoc network are active and passive. The incident within the network is an illustration of an active attack [10]. It can happen both alone and in combination. In MANET, dropping packets is also one of the factors that contribute to network failure. This failure occurs due to a fault occurring in the router. This type of attack is known as packet plumbing attack [11].

Figure 1 Sensor node

The sensor node mainly consists of the power supply unit (batteries), storage, transceiver, processor, and sensors as shown in Figure1. Additional units like location finding are used to find the node to transmit data to the desired node [12]. The Analog to Digital Converter converts analog signals to digital signals in the form of 0 and 1 and provides the data to the processing unit.

Figure 2 Single event occurs in MANET

As seen in Figure 2, node1 is a source node, whereas node4 is a destination node. Here, node3 is a node where the event has occurred to corrupt the desired information. When a source node wants to transmit

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data, it finds two nodes in its range one is node2 and other is node3. In Figure2, it has been seen that node3 give a response to node1 that this is the desired node and having the shortest path so you can transmit data to node3. In response from node3, node1 assuming that it is the desired node and start transmitting data [13]. In a mobile ad hoc network, this unwanted event will drop or consume the packets. The network operation is hampered by this issue since node3 can easily misroute packets. Ad hoc networks have a history of having trouble controlling events. Malicious occurrences now have a far higher chance of happening due to the passage of time. In such a circumstance, a competent mind that can make quick decisions is necessary [14]. The introduction of Feed Forward Back Propagation Neural Network under the "Levenberg Architecture" with different numbers of neurons is included in the problem statement of this study effort since artificial intelligence can be an excellent solution to this issue.

Figure 3 Feedforward multilayer back propagation network

Figure 3 consists of these input variables A_1, A_2, A_3 and a response variable B . At the input units, the inputs are connected to the neural network [15]. The weighted function w'_{mn} is then multiplied by the input variables. The hidden neuron then adds up the input neurons' weighted signals and sends the total to the activation function f_k . The outcome of the activation layer resulted from another multiplication with the weighted function w''_n . Send the output neurons your results after that. Additionally, the output neuron sums and projects the activation function f_0 . This response's output is represented by the symbol b^* . The output for a single output neuron may be calculated using the formula below.

$$b^* = f_0[P'' + \sum_{n=1}^{x_k} w''_n f_k(\sum_{m=1}^{x_r} w'_{mn} a_m + P')] \quad (1)$$

Here, P' & P'' are the biases of hidden neurons and output neurons.
 x_k & x_r are the number of input neurons and hidden neurons.

Calibration samples with known y are sent into the network during training. The error is then computed by comparing the predicted response to the known experimental response. The comparison is repeated until the low error is achieved.

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1.1 Quality of Service (QoS) support of ad hoc network

QoS differentiation in admission control and recover from congestion. Due to the mobility of the users in ad hoc networks, self-organization of the terminals linked to the backbone networks, and the absence of a central node with knowledge of the network resources, QoS support has become a significant difficulty in ad hoc networks [16]. Thus, QoS must be implemented in a distributed fashion, with mechanism for fast reacting to the mobility of the nodes.

EXISTING METHOD

This section explains the work done by a number of authors in their respective field. It is defined below, and the comparative analysis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparative Analysis of Existing Techniques

Reference	Title	Technique used	Outcomes
In [12]	Design and Optimization for Energy-Efficient Cooperative MIMO Transmission in Ad Hoc Networks	CMIMO-SMR strategy was used	A comparison with other strategies in terms of energy reduction has been done. Parameters like the number of hops and BER were investigated for energy minimization.
In [15]	Accurate Per-Packet Delay Tomography in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks	SDP relaxation technique, Time window, and graph cut method	Domo reconstructs per-hop per-packet delays by solving a set of optimization problems. The efficiency of Demo is improved using SDP. To deal with a large number of unknowns, graph cut method and Time window methods are used. Implementation is done on Tiny OS. The result shows that Demo gets high accuracy as compared with two related methods.
In [16]	Optimization of Routing Algorithms in Ad hoc Networks using Swarm Intelligence	FITANT, ARA, and MODANT are used.	MORDANT gives us the optimal path from source to destination with minimum connection time as compared to ARA and FITMENT. FITMENT provides a more reliable path.
In [17]	Partially Distributed Dynamic Model for Secure and Reliable Routing in Mobile Ad hoc	Dynamic time-out-based mechanism	Proposed a partially distributed dynamic model for security against misbehaving

nodes and ensured secure routing in mobile ad hoc networks.

Communication with the misbehaving node is blocked in order to provide security.

In [1] has been described a theoretical framework for an open system for secure wireless ad hoc networks is designed to provide precise guarantees. At the start of network activity, the unsynchronized node is utilized to join the system. The framework is a zero-sum game between all protocols and the filing strategy, with the filing strategy coming first in the announcement of the agreement. Every filing approach and option agreement will be profitable. The author has proposed a 'marginal unified supervision' of the merger agreement; the three aspects are important in theory.

In [2] investigated a full-duplex transmission capacity based on the random geometry of the self-organizing network. Full-duplex wireless devices may exchange data concurrently on the same frequency band and are a more conventional type of half-duplex node. The link model has successfully decoded the packet rate and attained the network's transmission capacity by studying the physical model and link protocol. The author further maximizes network throughput to determine the optimal transmission probability and quantify the potential benefits of a full-duplex node. The author has concluded that a full-duplex network covers the whole of the half-duplex transmission capacity, only with a relatively small distance paired link. With the growth of the pair of link distance, full-duplex transmission network capacity gain begins to drop.

In [3] addressed the various load measurements and some of the load balancing concepts that underlie the ad hoc routing protocols such as ABR, LBAR, LARA, CSLAR, TSA, and LAOR. For load modeling, only LBAR and ABR have been applied. While other protocols were employed for route discovery, LBAR and ABR handled load balancing during route maintenance.

In [9] described a distributed routing policy with congestion diversity (D-ORCD) using a combination of backpressure routing and the essential elements of the shortest route. With the help of this policy, packets are routed in accordance with the nodes' rank ordering based on a congestion metric. The performance of the authors' suggested practical distributed and asynchronous 802.11 compliant D-ORCD implementations was examined using a thorough set of QualNet simulations for real-world networks. According to simulation data, D-ORCD routinely outperforms the current routing.

In [13] created a MANET routing protocol. Authors have discovered several divergent approaches that are the most trustworthy. To determine the most trustworthy path set, the authors employed the Hopfield neural network. In MANET, when speed and space are crucial factors, the Hopfield neural network employed an analog circuit that is quick and compact. Routing overhead is reduced by discovering several pathways during single route discovery. An approach that computed link-disjoint and node-disjoint route sets was employed by the authors. Link-disjoint path sets are more reliable than node-disjoint ones, according to simulations. Node-disjoint route sets perform better in terms of lifespan when nodes fail in the network. When compared to the shortest route algorithm, the suggested technique has demonstrated an average lifespan that is two times longer. In addition, compared to the Backup Path set Selection (BPS) technique, the suggested approach delivers a reliability gain of 29%.

PROPOSED WORK

The proposed work is divided into three sections namely the route discovery process, event management and evaluation of the QoS parameters. The proposed algorithm has been named as Smart Event Management for Ad hoc Network (SEMAN).

3.1 Route Discovery Mechanism

The nodes must be moved and their coverage set must be determined as part of the route discovery method. The algorithmic structure of the route discovery process is as follows:

Algorithm 1 Creating Node properties

```
Function [energy_pn, energy_cpn, packetd, delayn, smartnetworknetwork] =
createnodeproperties(nodes) // This function generates the properties of nodes that need to be
distributed in the network
smartnetworknetwork= []; // smart network is the ad hoc network that includes node information
for j=1: nodes // this represents the total number of network nodes.
    energy_pn(j)=50*random; // generating random values for the energy which the nodes already have
    energy_cpn(j)=10*random; // this is how much energy a node uses if it is engaged in a process
    packetd(j)=30*random; // typically, when the network loses some packets, a random value is set
    delayn(j)=30*random;
end
smartnetworknetwork. energy_pn=energy_pn;
smartnetworknetwork. energy_cpn=energy_cpn;
smartnetworknetwork. packetd=packetd;
smartnetworknetwork. delayn=delayn;
savenodeproperty
end
```

Algorithm 2 Discovering coverage set of nodes in the network

```
Function [CoverageSet, path] =DiscoverPathandCoverage (nodes, a, b)
// a and b is the combined GPS position of a node
// nodes is the total number of nodes
for ssi=1: num_el(totala) // total a locations
    destn=smartnetwork.destination; // random destination of the network
    if ssi~=smartnetwork.destination
        distance=sqrt((totala(ssi)-totala(destn))^2+(totalb(ssi)-totalb(destn))^2); // this is the distance formula
        to calculate the distance between the destination and any other node
        if distance < 200 // the coverage range has been set at 200 metres because the network's overall
        width is 1000 metres.
            d_mat(d_matcount)=ssi;
            d_matcount=d_matcount+1;
        end
    end
end
```

Algorithm 3 Applications of the Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm

```
Function [alternative node] = function Apply ABC (Effected Node, Coverage Set of Target, Target,
Energy Consumption of nodes)
Bee_pop = Total number of nodes in the target's coverage set.
Employed Bee = Current Node in the list
Onlooker Bee = Threshold set for node selection
Possiblelist = []; // total number of possible nodes
Possiblecount = 0;
for i=1: nodesinlist
    Empb=nodelist(i);
    Empbe=energy(Empb);
```


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```
Onlookerb=mean(Energyofnodes);  
if (Empbe<Onlookerb)  
    Possiblelist[Possiblecount]=Empb;  
    Possiblecount=possiblecount+1;  
End if  
End for  
End Function
```

Algorithm 1 creates random values for the purpose of deploying a random ad hoc network. Once this has been applied, a node network with random node values will be created. The random values were chosen to introduce uncertainty into the network and demonstrate how well the suggested technique works.

Algorithm 2 is made to determine the network nodes' coverage set. The coverage set serves as an example of which node may be chosen as a routing path element.

The simulated path where the source transmits the data packet to a node that is relatively near to the destination is identified using the output of Algorithm 2. The distance formula has been used for the same objective. The route is provided by Algorithm 2 as follows:

Route (1) =Source; // the source would be the first component in the route.
Route (2) = Middle Element // A node that is closer to the target would be the middle element.
Route (3) =Target // the data will be transmitted to the target through the middle element.

Algorithm 3 is the application of an optimization algorithm in order to choose an alternative node if any node is affected by any event or is not able to transfer the data to the corresponding target.

In general, the ABC algorithm is a substantial part of swarm intelligence computing and is often used to reduce the complexity of the data [17]. Here, in this proposed algorithm, the ABC is used to select the appropriate alternative node.

3.2 Event Management

ABC algorithm can only depict the possible alternative node to transfer the data, but this does not solve the event management problem. For this purpose, Levenberg Neural Network is trained using the network features which are not influenced by any event or intrusion. The following architecture is observed.

Figure 4 A block schematic for training a neural network

Figure 5 Neural Network training explanation block diagram

Figure 6 Neural Network training performance block diagram

In the above, Figure 4 is for the training of neural networks trained with different illumination. The detailed description is shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. After training, a snapshot of the neural network is displayed in Fig. 5, and Fig. 6 displays the neural network's performance. The network is trained at the first iteration which has been evaluated using the energy pattern of the nodes. The network is then simulated using the affected region's energy pattern, and it returns the exactly affected node in the network, and then the affected node is then barred from any kind of routing activity. Later on, the network can be rectified.

3.3 Evaluation of the QoS parameters

Quality of Service (QoS) metrics would be used to evaluate the suggested algorithm's solution. The parameters to be anticipated are:

- a. Error Rate
- b. Throughput

SIMULATION RESULTS

Number of nodes	Table 2 Simulation Setting 50-100
Area	1000-1000 meters
Simulation Tool	MATLAB
Authentication Parameter	Energy Consumption
Evaluation Parameter	Throughput, Error Rate

In above, Table 2 displays the simulation setting for the proposed task.

After the neural network is set up and the erroneous node is prohibited and sent for the rectification shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, the following simulation outcomes have been shown.

Figure 7 Comparison of Throughput

Figure 8 Comparison of Error Rate

In this work, a total of 5 iterations/rounds have been simulated, and the results show signified that the growth in the throughput of the network as the packet delivery ratio obviously increases. The average growth is about 30 to 40 percent. The proposed algorithm shows the maximum error rate that is 9.4 % at maximum whereas for normal behavior it is observed as 28 %.

CONCLUSION

The suggested SEMAN algorithm not only resolves the issue of determining a different path in the event that a network error occurs, but it also locates the problematic node and sends it back to the base station for repair. Throughput and Error Rate are the two key metrics used to assess the network's performance, with energy consumption serving as a key metric for optimization and alternate path discovery. The ABC method has been used to analyze the alternate route, and neural networks have been used for identification and mitigation. Many doors are opened for future researchers by the current study endeavor. The next step is to adjust the number of iterations while also altering the total number of neurons in the network, and then observe the results.

Acknowledgment

This entire research is fully dedicated to Chandigarh University which made me capable to complete the research and provided me with all required resources. We thank our colleagues from Chandigarh University who provided insight and expertise that greatly assisted the research, although they may not agree with all of the interpretations/conclusions of this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Ponniah J, Yin CH, Kumar PR. A Clean Slate Approach to Secure Ad Hoc Wireless Networking-Open Unsynchronized Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems*. 2017 March, 4(1), PP. 37-48.
2. Qin D, Ding Z. Transport Capacity Analysis of Wireless In-Band Full Duplex Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*. 2017 March, 65(3), pp. 1303-1318.
3. C.K Toh, Chai K, Anh L, ze YC. Load-balanced routing protocols for ad hoc mobile wireless networks in *IEEE Communications Magazine*. 2009 August, 47(8), pp. 78-84.
4. Wang Y, Chen IR, Cho JH, Tsai JJP. Trust-Based Task Assignment with Multi-Objective Optimization in Service-Oriented Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*. 2017 March, 14(1), pp. 217-232.
5. Bader A, Alouini MS. Mobile Ad Hoc Networks in Bandwidth-Demanding Mission-Critical Applications. *Practical Implementation Insights*. *IEEE Access*. 2017, 5(9), pp. 891-910.

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6. MadanR, Mehta NB, MolischA F, Zhang J. Energy-Efficient Decentralized Cooperative Routing in Wireless Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*. 2009 March, 54(3), pp. 512-527.
7. Skjelsvik KS, Goebel V, Plagemann T. Distributed Event Notification for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Distributed Systems Online* published by the IEEE Computer society. 2004 Aug, 5(8), pp. 2-2.
8. Prashar L, Kapur. RK. Performance analysis of routing protocols under different types of attacks in MANETs. 5th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions) (ICRITO), Noida. 2016, pp. 405-408.
9. Bhorkar A, Naghshvar M, Javidi T. Opportunistic Routing with Congestion Diversity in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*. 2016 April, 24(2), pp. 1167-1180.
10. Seet C, Lee BS, Lau CT. On optimizing route discovery of topology-based on-demand routing protocols for ad hoc networks. *Journal of Communications and Networks*. 2003 Sept, 5(3) pp. 266-274.
11. Yang S, Cheng, Wang HF. Genetic Algorithms with Immigrants and Memory Schemes for Dynamic Shortest Path Routing Problems in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*. 2010 Jan, 40(1), pp. 52-63.
12. Peng Y, Al-Hazemi F, Kim H, Youn CH. Design and Optimization for Energy-Efficient Cooperative MIMO Transmission in Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*. 2017 Jan, 66(1), pp. 710-719.
13. Sheikhan, Hemmati ME. High reliable disjoint path set selection in a mobile ad-hoc network using Hopfield neural network. *IET Communications*. 2011 July, pp. 1566-1576.
14. Ghosh, Uttam, Datta R. A Secure Addressing Scheme for Large-Scale Managed MANETs. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*. 2015 Sept, 12(3), pp. 483-495.
15. Gao Y, Dong W, Chen C, Zhang X, Bu J, Liu X. Accurate Per-Packet Delay Tomography in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*. 2017 Feb, 25(1), pp. 480-491.
16. Kumar S, Chaudhary R. Optimization of routing algorithms in ad-hoc networks using swarm intelligence. *World Congress on Information and Communication Technologies*, Mumbai. 2011, pp. 677-681.
17. Anand A, Aggarwal H, Rani R. Partially distributed dynamic model for secure and reliable routing in mobile ad hoc networks. *Journal of Communications and Networks*. 2016 Dec, 18(6), pp. 938-947.

